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Dear subscribers,

EU4Advice and COREnet are proud to continue working together toward a shared vision: establishing a strong European network of short food supply chain advisors integrated into national AKIS. This collaboration is built on a foundation of shared resources, expertise, and a commitment to driving meaningful change across Europe's food systems.

Over the past months, our joint efforts have focused on expanding networks, engaging advisors, and showcasing best practices. Looking ahead to 2025, we are preparing for exciting new initiatives, including joint events, policy related events, training content release, enhanced advisor mapping, and activities to promote knowledge sharing and collaboration across countries. These efforts will ensure that the solutions and insights generated by both projects reach stakeholders far and wide.

Together, EU4Advice and COREnet are stronger, delivering impactful results that benefit advisors, producers, farmers and communities across Europe. Thank you for being part of this journey.

Patricia Mora McGinity
Project Coordinator, EU4Advice

Joint News Section

Cross Living Lab Event: Co-Innovation in Urban Challenges

From July 1st to July 3rd, the Cross Living Lab event, hosted by one of EU4Advice's partners, Amped, brought together experts and stakeholders to collaborate on urban and food solutions. This event counted by the presence of some COREnet representatives, and used the "Living Lab" approach, where different stakeholders work together to test, develop, and create solutions for complex metropolitan challenges. [Read more!](#)

The COREnet Experience at the Cross Living Labs Amsterdam

Eva Jennings

Research Office in the Rural Economy
& Development Programme (REDP)

Jan Willem van der Schans

Co-Founder Task Force Korte Ketten
(Task Force Short Supply Chain)

The COREnet Experience at the EU4Advice Cross Living Labs Event in the Netherlands

At the beginning of July, Eva Jennings and Jan Willem Van Der Schans, representatives of COREnet, attended the EU4Advice Cross Living Lab event in the Netherlands. This event, organised by Amped, gathered experts from various European Living Labs to exchange knowledge and explore new opportunities for cooperation.

[Read More](#)

COREnet 2nd European Roadshow

Hosted by InLoco, the COREnet team has spent two inspiring and fruitful days in Faro, Portugal, for the second project European Roadshow. Patricia Mora, EU4Advice coordinator, was invited to a round table discussion as key expert in the field.

[Read more](#)

#FairFoodRevolution campaign

CLEVERFOOD, with the participation of EU4Advice and COREnet, launched the "Food is for Everyone: Shaping the European Food System for a #FairFoodRevolution" campaign on LinkedIn to advocate for healthy, sustainable, and affordable food as a fundamental right. Running from October 1 to October 18 in alignment with #WorldFoodDay, the campaign invited everyone to share their own experiences and stories on this important issue.

[Check the campaign](#)

EU4Advice marks key milestones with successful General Assembly and Review Meeting

In September, EU4Advice achieved significant milestones with the successful completion of its General Assembly and review meeting. During the General Assembly, partners came together to assess the project's progress, share insights, and discuss next steps for advancing the European network of short food supply chain advisors. The review meeting provided an opportunity to reflect on achievements, address challenges, and fine-tune strategies moving forward.

[GA article](#)[Review Meeting](#)

Events

Funded by
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EU4Advice took part in events to advance Sustainable Food Systems and Advisor Networks

EU4Advice recently participated in several impactful events that highlight its ongoing commitment to advancing the European network of short food supply chain advisors. These included the Reformaten conference, where key discussions on food system transformation took place, and the Synergy Days, which fostered collaboration between EU projects. EU4Advice also contributed to Ireland's Agrifood System Workshop, exploring sustainable practices, and the Feeding Ourselves event, which focused on local food security. Additionally, the Resilient Smallholder Initiative webinar brought together experts to discuss how to support smallholders in building resilience. These events are integral to EU4Advice's mission to promote knowledge sharing and drive positive change in Europe's food systems.

[Check the past and future events here](#)

Report on Developing Infrastructure for Short Food Supply Chains

Report on Developing Infrastructure for Short Food Supply Chains

On February 20, 2024, Newcastle University hosted a workshop on creating practical strategies to enhance the infrastructure for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs).

[Read the report](#)

Testimonials' series

**Julia Gómez-Lama
Gutierrez**

Graduated with an MSc in Biology and Science
Communication and Society, Leiden University

#EU4AdviceTestimonials Julia Gómez-Lama Gutiérrez

The valuable insights and experiences will help us showcase the project's impact and foster deeper connections within our community. This campaign is an exciting opportunity to highlight the voices that drive our mission forward.

[Learn more](#)

COREnet Latest News

Fostering advisory services innovation on SFSC: Highlights from the first COREnet European Roadshow

On the 26th of June the COREnet project has organised its first European Roadshow, an hybrid event which involved key SFSC stakeholders who actively participated both in Cagliari, at the Coldiretti headquarter, and online.

The European Roadshow is an event which showcases the results and characteristics of the COREnet Golden Cases, offering participants the chance to learn how advisory practices from the Golden Cases lead to improved performance and impact.

[Read the article](#)

COREnet Showcases Italian SFSC Advisory Successes in Cagliari Field Visits

COREnet coordinator, Fedele Colantuono (University of Foggia) was invited to present the project during the event organised by CREA (Italian Research Center in Agricultural Economics), where results from the projects i2connect, Attractiss, modernAKIS and EUfarmbook were shared.

The event took place in Rome on October 28-29 and was coordinated by Patrizia Proietti and Simona Cristiano, researchers at CREA. They are actively engaged in the aforementioned Horizon-funded initiatives, focusing on advisory services in the agrifood sector and fostering interactive co-creation, training, networking, and transnational peer-to-peer learning at the EU level.

[Read more](#)

COREnet Advances Advisory Practices for the Italian Community at the CREA Conference

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[Read more](#)

Interviews

In this section, we will share a selection of interviews conducted by each project. These conversations offer valuable insights into the experiences, achievements, and perspectives of those working to advance the goals of EU4Advice and COREnet.

An interview with the EU4Advice Coordinator

Patricia Mora McGinity

[Watch the interview](#)

An interview with Eva Jennings

[Watch it](#)

EU4Advice Living Labs interviews

Listen to the Netherlands, Spain, Hungary and Ireland Eu4Advice Living Labs leaders.

[Watch the playlist](#)

An Interview with Claudio Orefice

[Watch it](#)

Joint Future Event

Supporting Local Food Systems and innovation in BIOEAST countries

Venue: Budapest, Hungary - Central European University
(Nádor street 9. 1051)

DATE: 4th December 2024. 09:30-16:00

Join us at the EU4Advice & COREnet & CleverFood Conference Policy Workshop on the 4th December 2024, at Central European University, Budapest, Hungary, from 09:30 to 16:00.

[Learn more](#)

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The SFS Innovation Platform is an online environment for those who want to stay up-to-date and/or grow their activities!

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